

Validation of the Power Deposition Methodology used for Conversion Analyses of the RHF Reactor

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ABSTRACT

The Institut Laue Langevin (ILL) high flux reactor (RHF), located in France, is dedicated to neutron scattering experiments and radioisotopes production. The core consists of a single, compact fuel assembly containing highly enriched uranium (HEU, $^{235}\text{U}/\text{U} \geq 20$ wt. %) fuel. Because of its compactness, a non-negligible amount of power is deposited outside the fuel region, and this must be quantified for thermal-hydraulics analyses. Argonne National Laboratory (ANL) has been collaborating with ILL for over a decade on the conversion of the reactor to the use of low-enriched uranium (LEU, $^{235}\text{U}/\text{U} < 20$ wt. %) fuel, which requires a new assembly design that meets all performance and safety criteria. To assess the design, a method accounting for the main contributors of fission power is used to calculate the power deposition in the RHF reactor. The RHF main cooling circuit splits into two flow paths resulting in heating from different regions of the core. Pressure, temperature and flow measurements allow for an accurate estimation of the power deposition in these regions at all times during the cycle, thereby providing a unique opportunity to validate the power deposition method. Numerical simulation of power deposition in the core of an actual operating cycle has been performed, taking into account burnup effects and control rod motion, and compared to experimental data. A very good agreement is observed which indicates that the method employed for evaluating the power deposition in the RHF core is valid and can be used in conversion analysis.

Keywords: HEU, LEU, RHF, conversion, validation

1. INTRODUCTION

The Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL) is a research center located in Grenoble, France, funded by France, Germany and the United Kingdom. Since 1971, it has operated the High Flux Reactor (RHF), which has a compact core designed to produce a high thermal neutron flux (1×10^{15} n/cm²/s). This powerful neutron source is used for fundamental science and radioisotope production [1].

The core is made of a single, compact fuel assembly that has an annular shape. The annular assembly, depicted in Figure 1, is filled with fuel plates curved as an involute welded to inner and outer aluminum side-plates (tubes). The fuel assembly is located in the middle of a heavy water reflector that contains experimental devices and safety rods. The control rod is in the center of the annular-shaped assembly.

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The reactor is cooled and moderated by heavy water. From the inlet pipe, located above the core, the coolant flows downward, first through a chimney. Then, at the inlet of the fuel assembly, the flow splits into two paths: one to cool the annular fuel assembly, the other to cool the central control rod. The flow through the fuel assembly, hereafter referred to as the main flow, represents ~97% of the total. It exits at the bottom of the fuel assembly and then flows into the reflector tank and leaves at the top of the reflector tank. The remaining 3% of coolant flows through the control rod and will be referred to as the control rod flow. After reaching the bottom of the control rod housing, the coolant exits via dedicated piping, pumps and heat exchangers before rejoining with the main flow. Pressure, temperature and flow rate are measured at the inlet and outlet of these circuits, allowing calculation of the power deposited in them and therefore the power deposited in different regions of the core. The coolant flowing through the control rod is heated by neutrons and gamma energy deposited in the control rod and central cavity (structure + heavy water). The main flow is heated by energy deposited in the fuel assembly, reflector, and all devices located within the reflector tank. A schematic of the reactor and coolant flow paths is provided in Figure 2.

The current fuel system is made of U-Al_x particles compacted within an aluminum matrix. It has a relatively low uranium density but high enrichment (> 20 wt. %). Aligning with non-proliferation policies, the ILL is pursuing conversion to a higher-density, LEU fuel, made of U₃Si₂ fuel particles, which requires a new design that satisfies performance and safety criteria.

Conversion analyses rely on validated codes and methods. Argonne is collaborating with ILL on reactor conversion and provides technical support as needed. ILL and Argonne use the Monte Carlo code MCNP [2] and the depletion code VESTA [3] for performing reactor physics analyses. A key outcome of this collaboration was the development of a highly detailed MCNP model that was benchmarked against experimental data. The model reproduces with high accuracy several parameters of interest, such as neutron flux and reactivity evolution [1].

Figure 1. Schematic of RHF Fuel Assembly: (a) Vertical cross-section; (b) 3D representation of the fuel plate; (c) Top view cross section; (d) Detailed top view cross section. Source: Modified from [4].

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Figure 2. Schematic vertical cross section of the reactor and flow paths.

An important output of reactor physics analyses is an estimation of the distribution of power deposition in the core in time and space as it is used as input for thermal-hydraulic analyses. Section 2 describes the MCNP based method used to estimate power deposition. This method relies on several assumptions and simplifications. The purpose of this validation analysis is to assess its accuracy and estimate the associated power uncertainty.

Exploiting the operational data collected during an actual cycle, it was possible to calculate the actual power deposited in the control rod and main flow regions of the reactor (Section 3). Numerical simulations of this cycle were performed and power deposited in these two reactor regions was calculated at multiple time points. Because the control rod moves over time, the power deposited in the control rod evolves, which is captured in the simulations. Calculation results are provided and discussed in Section 4.

2. POWER DEPOSITION METHOD

The total nuclear energy released during the fission process originates from multiple sources:

- Kinetic energy of the fission fragments.
- Kinetic energy of prompt and delayed neutrons.
- Prompt and delayed gamma energy.
- Fission product beta decay energy.
- Capture gamma energy from (n,γ) reactions.
- Antineutrinos.

Except for the antineutrinos, all sources listed above will contribute to the heat deposition in the reactor and therefore must be accounted for. Explicit modeling is, however, difficult to achieve in practice as it requires transporting various types of particles and tracking reactions on various time scales. To circumvent this difficulty, simplifying assumptions can be employed to estimate the fission power deposition without explicit modeling of delayed power contributors (i.e., beta decay and delayed gammas). While the amount of energy they release per fission is known and can be obtained from nuclear data files, the locations where this energy is deposited are not. For example, the ENDF/B VII.1 library reports delayed beta and gammas energy from the thermal fission of ^{235}U as 6.5 MeV and 6.33 MeV per fission, respectively.

The energy released from the beta decay of the fission products is deposited locally in the fissioning regions. The distribution of this energy would logically follow the fission distribution, which can be easily estimated. The delayed gammas, while also originating from the fissioning regions, transport their energy, potentially, everywhere. Considering that the average energy and multiplicity of the prompt and delayed gammas is similar, it is reasonable to assume that the delayed gamma energy distribution follows the distribution of the prompt gammas, which can also be easily calculated. Implementation of these two simplifying but reasonable assumptions provide a means to estimate the local deposition of power in fissile and non-fissile regions alike without explicit modeling of delayed beta and gammas.

Implementation of delayed beta and gamma energy deposition in MCNP models has been described elsewhere [5]. A non-exhaustive literature review indicates that this method has been applied to various problems [6]. Interestingly, other widely used Monte Carlo neutron and photon transport codes such as SERPENT implemented power deposition estimators that make use of the same approximations [7].

Practical implementation of this method in MCNP requires use of multiple heating tallies and scaling operations and two separate calculations. In a first calculation, the F6 heating tally is used to calculate the energy per fission deposited in any given cell. The F6 tally accounts for contribution from fission fragments, prompt and delayed neutrons, and prompt and capture gammas. By default, MCNP photon transport does not separate prompt and capture gammas. In a separate run, and using the MCNP PIKMT option, it is possible to select the isotopes emitting gammas. By limiting the gamma creation to fissile isotopes only, the prompt gamma distribution can be obtained. It can then be scaled to the total delayed gamma energy of 6.33 MeV/fission to estimate the delayed gamma energy deposition. The local beta energy deposition is obtained by scaling the F7 tally, which estimates the fission power where it has been generated, to the total delayed beta energy of 6.5 MeV/fission.

In practice, the power deposition in all regions of the RHF model is calculated, which allows estimation of the power contributing to heating the coolant in the main and control rod flow paths described in Section 1 and illustrated in Figure 2.

3. OPERATING CYCLE 143

As explained previously, the RHF core is made of only one fuel assembly, always fresh at the beginning of a new cycle. In addition, all solid structures in the reflector visible to neutrons during normal operation are either made of aluminum or zircaloy, mostly transparent to neutrons; irradiation evolution of these structures can therefore be reasonably ignored. The control rod's reactivity worth does evolve from cycle to cycle and must be replaced periodically. Cycles making use of a new control rod are particularly useful, because for those, the reactor core can be considered entirely fresh, which is very easy to model and minimizes biases. Operation cycle 143 is one of those cycles and has been selected to perform the benchmark.

The power evolution of cycle 143 is depicted in Figure 3. This cycle lasted for 45 days, which is typical. This figure shows the power in the main and control rod regions as well. It can be seen that the total power was very stable in this cycle and that the heat deposited in the fuel assembly and reflector (heating the main loop coolant) represents a very large fraction of the total (~98.2% cycle-average). While relatively small in comparison, the heat deposited in the control rod loop amounted to ~1.0 MW (cycle-average), which is not negligible.

Figure 3. Power evolution in RHF cycle 143.

4. NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF CYCLE 143

Monte Carlo depletion analyses of cycle 143 were performed using MCNP and VESTA with the control rod automatically set to the time-dependent critical control rod position. Numerical simulations showed very good agreement in the predicted time-dependent critical control rod position, giving confidence in the model. Details of the modeling have been described elsewhere [1].

Calculation of the power deposition per source and location of interest obtained at beginning of cycle is presented in Table I. The kinetic energy of the fission fragments and the beta decay energy that follows is entirely deposited in the fuel and represent almost 87% of the total recoverable energy per fission. The gamma energy (from prompt, delayed and neutron capture) represents 10.7% of the total and only 36.5% of this is deposited in the fuel assembly. The prompt and delayed neutron energy represents only ~2.5% of the total with only 40% deposited in the fuel assembly.

The power deposited in the control rod and its surroundings (heating up the control rod loop coolant) is distributed as follows: approximately 58% from the prompt and delayed gammas, 24% from the prompt and delayed neutrons, and about 18% from capture gammas.

Table I. Calculated energy per fission deposition per source and location at beginning of cycle.

Recoverable energy per fission from... (MeV/fission)	Fuel assembly	Reflector	Control rod & structures	Other structures	Total	Fraction of total
kinetic energy of fission products	169.12	0.00	0.00	0.00	169.12	83.7%
prompt & delayed neutrons	2.01	2.14	0.82	0.00	4.97	2.5%
prompt gammas	3.95	2.98	1.10	0.13	8.16	4.0%
Gammas from (n,γ) reactions	0.85	2.82	0.59	2.78	7.04	3.5%
beta decay	6.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.5	3.2%
delayed gammas	3.07	2.31	0.86	0.10	6.33	3.1%
<i>total =</i>	<i>185.50</i>	<i>10.24</i>	<i>3.37</i>	<i>3.02</i>	<i>202.12</i>	<i>100%</i>
<i>fraction of total =</i>	<i>91.8%</i>	<i>5.1%</i>	<i>1.7%</i>	<i>1.5%</i>	<i>100.0%</i>	

The same calculations have been repeated at different time steps in the cycle. The evolution of the power deposited in the control rod loop obtained from these calculations has been compared to the operation data of cycle 143. The results are shown in Figure 4. This figure reveals that the calculated power is very close to the actual power measured in this location with a maximum deviation of 0.1% with respect to the total power, which is very satisfactory considering the many power contributors to take into account in this calculation.

The power deposited in the control rod decreases slightly during irradiation, from 1.9 to 1.7% of the total power. This is an expected result: as the control rod is withdrawn during the cycle, the amount of

power deposited in the solid structure progressively reduces over time. This is well captured by the simulations as the calculated power follows closely the operation data.

Figure 4. Comparison of calculated and actual fraction of total power deposited in the control rod loop.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this work is to validate the power deposition method used in conversion analyses of the RHF reactor. The method makes use of reasonable simplifications to account for all pertinent contributors to fission power. Specific design features of the RHF cooling systems allow measuring power deposited from two distinct regions of the core. High-fidelity Monte Carlo depletion model of the reactor allows calculating the evolution of the power in these two regions.

Comparative analyses demonstrate that the power deposition method used in conversion analyses is capable of reproducing operation data very well (within 0.1%). This important result provides confidence in the numerical schemes employed for conversion analysis.

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